

Progress on an Implantable Microphone for Cochlear Implants

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Abstract. We present the development and evaluation of an implantable middle-ear microphone, named UmboMic, for fully implanted cochlear implants. We test the UmboMic in five human cadaveric ears. Results demonstrate consistent microphone performance across sensors and across ears, regardless of slight fabrication differences or anatomical ear variations. The UmboMic has high sensitivity and the equivalent input noise is comparable to external hearing aid microphones.

INTRODUCTION

Cochlear implants are devices that can enable hearing for people with sensorineural deafness. Despite their name, cochlear implants rely on an external unit which contains components such as a microphone. Due to this external unit, cochlear implants cannot be used during sleep and vigorous activity, are susceptible to noise from wind, and function poorly in loud environments. Implanting the entire device would mitigate these problems and provide users with the discretion of an invisible device. An implanted microphone would also enable benefits from the filtering and pressure boost of the outer ear. We present the design, fabrication, and testing of an implantable middle-ear microphone called the “UmboMic.”

The UmboMic is a piezoelectric displacement sensor that is implanted in the middle-ear cavity and contacts the umbo. The umbo is the point where the malleus attaches to the center of the tympanic membrane. We target the umbo because its unidirectional motion produces a well-represented sound signal at most auditory frequencies. As the umbo moves, it displaces the UmboMic, resulting in a charge that is amplified with a custom amplifier. Our design contrasts the MED-EL Mi2000 microphone [1], which consists of a microphone implanted under the skin near the pinna. It also differs from the Envoy Acclaim piezoelectric microphone [2], which targets the incus rather than the umbo.

We fabricate the UmboMic from two thin layers of piezoelectric polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF). The biomorphic design reduces common mode noise and aids in rejecting electromagnetic interference. Furthermore, we use titanium as our conductive material for biocompatibility. After fabrication, we test sensors on the bench with an “artificial umbo” as well as in human cadaveric specimens. We present the fabrication and testing of seven sensors in five cadaveric ears to demonstrate fabrication consistency and microphone reliability in different anatomy. This expands upon our previous work in [3], which only showed data for one sensor in one ear. Furthermore, we confirm that progress towards biocompatibility by using safe materials does not degrade microphone performance.

METHODS

A custom flex printed circuit board (PCB) functions as the core substrate for the sensor. The flex PCB simplifies connecting the sensor to the amplifier and is a temporary solution to ease prototyping. The main difference between this version of the UmboMic and the earlier UmboMic presented in [3] is the use of titanium as the conductive material, and a final layer of Parylene C for waterproofing. The switch from aluminum to titanium is an important step in making the UmboMic biocompatible. Figure 1 shows a picture of an unfinished and finished umboMic sensor, while Figure 2 illustrates the material cross section of the sensor.

FIGURE 1: A picture of two UmboMic sensors. The top sensor is partially fabricated: the triangular electrodes have been patterned, the flex PCB trimmed, and the PVDF layer adhered. It is missing the ground shield and U.FL connector which can be seen in the finished bottom sensor.

FIGURE 2: A diagram of the UmboMic sensor stack up after fabrication.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

We conduct cadaveric experiments in a sound-proofed and electrically-isolated chamber at Mass Eye and Ear. All measurements occur on an air table to minimize vibrational noise. The fresh human cadaveric ears are sourced from Massachusetts General Hospital. Surgical preparation of the specimens allows access to the middle-ear cavity, similar to cochlear implant surgery. A sinusoidal tone sweep from 0.1-20 kHz is introduced to the ear canal. This sound is measured at the ear canal using a probe tube microphone (Knowles EK3103) with the tip 1-2 mm from the tympanic membrane. The velocity of the umbo is measured with laser Doppler vibrometry (LDV) through the ear canal. From the middle-ear cavity, the UmboMic sensor and custom differential amplifier detect umbo motion resulting in charge. The UmboMic sensor is held in the mastoid cavity by a custom flexure clamp attached to a manipulator.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cadaveric Testing

We test our sensors in five cadaveric ears. Figure 3 shows the frequency response of all seven sensors in one of these ears. Figure 4 overlays the frequency response of sensor Ti-4 in all five ears. The y-axis shows the charge output of the sensor normalized by the measured stimulus ear canal sound pressure. The UmboMic sensitivity is high up

FIGURE 3: The frequency response of seven sensors in one human cadaveric ear.

to the target of 8 kHz, and the frequency response is very flat up to and above 1 kHz. Around 1 kHz to 2 kHz, the magnitude peaks, and the phase decreases. The resonance of the umbo at these frequencies is well established in [4] [5] [6]. Around 2-4 kHz, there is a 20-40 dB/dec roll off in sensor sensitivity due to the change in umbo motion. In all of the ears, the sensitivity above 8 kHz is still within 15 dB of the flat lower frequency sensitivity below 1 kHz. The anatomical differences between ears can account for much of the variability between experiments with the same sensors.

Figure 4 highlights the consistency of a single sensor across different ears. The sensor amplitude below 1 kHz is similar across experiments. Above this frequency, the unique motion of the umbo of each ear means that the response is different between experiments.

Equivalent Input Noise

The equivalent input noise (EIN) of the microphone and amplifier is an important metric for determining the minimum sound it can sense. Figure 5 plots the EIN of our system against that of the commercially-available Knowles EK3103 hearing aid microphone (shown in black). The dark blue line corresponds to EIN data from our microphone in Ear 2 without the outer ear. The light blue line shows the decreased EIN after considering the increase in pressure gain due to the outer ear [6] [7]. The A-weighted EIN of the Knowles microphone, our microphone, and our microphone with the outer ear are 33.8 dB SPL, 43.3 dB SPL, and 32.4 dB SPL respectively. Thus, the UmboMic performs comparably to a commercially available microphone, and even better from 0.9 to 6 kHz. This result is very similar to what is presented in our previous paper [3], therefore proving that the use of titanium instead of aluminum does not increase the noise floor of our device.

FIGURE 4: The frequency response of sensor Ti-4 in each of these five ears.

FIGURE 5: Equivalent input noise (EIN) normalized to 1/3-octave bandwidth for the UmboMic with and without the outer ear and the the Knowles hearing aid microphone.

CONCLUSION

Developing an implantable microphone is the largest barrier to achieving a fully internal cochlear implant. We present the testing of the UmboMic, a piezoelectric microphone that senses motion of the umbo in the middle-ear. By using titanium and PVDF, we ensure that all active materials in our sensor are biocompatible. Through testing our microphone in five human cadaveric ears, we show that seven individually fabricated sensors behave similarly despite anatomical differences. All UmboMics have a flat frequency response up to 1 kHz and robust sensitivity above 8 kHz. These results indicate that the UmboMic can function well in a variety of patients. Furthermore, we show that the UmboMic has an EIN comparable to commercially available hearing aid microphones. This work demonstrates important progress towards a fully implanted cochlear implant.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

Allen, Jont: I have a simple suggestion. I used to record from the cat, and we would always measure the cochlear microphonic with a silver chloride electrode on the eardrum and we would also place it on the round window. One day I had the brilliant idea of hooking it up to an amplifier and seeing how it works and it has an amazing frequency response. It sounds better than any microphone. All you need is a little wire, you touch it to the round window and you’re done.

Raphael, Robert: How are you going to get all of the electronics in for signal processing. You visualize total implantation, right?

Wawrzynek, Emma: Our big focus right now is the microphone. The microphone also includes the custom amplifier which I did not talk about, and that of course has a lot of large electronics components. The plan is to integrate some of the first stage of the amplifier into the fixation hardware so it can be hermetically sealed there. Then we can have other parts of the amplifier somewhere near the sound processor which would be implanted further away. This can be done under the skin of the skull where there is more room. With the signal processor, we are not touching on that right now.

Rafael, Robert: What about power? You’d need an external battery, right?

Wawrzynek, Emma: Right, so we’ve talked with a couple of the cochlear implant companies and they’ve said we need to use at most 1mW of power, which we’ve achieved with our device. Our vision is integrating this with the cochlear implant company designs. Med-El and Cochlear are working on implanted microphones and powering the processor. We can use some of the power from the battery they’ve designed.

Ketten, Darlene: One question is longevity and compatibility with preexisting conditions, I'm thinking particular of cochlear implants in children and teenagers. But, with very young children, is there going to be a problem with the growing middle ear spaces?

Wawrzyniek, Emma: We are concerned about that, the ear could grow and this would be a problem. We are going to stay away from implanting in young children with our device since we can't account for that with our design.

Ketten, Darlene: Since I assume you are using all adult cadaveric specimen.

Wawrzyniek, Emma: Yes.

Bergevin, Chris: Based upon your gut feeling and what you know, do you think people with this kind of thing would be more or less susceptible to changes in their hearing when they have a cold or something like that?

Wawrzyniek, Emma: I would maybe guess more susceptible, we haven't tested that. Versus a healthy individual? It's a good question. We talk about it a little bit.

Hajicek, Joshua: Along the lines of Chris, what about negative middle ear pressure, like excessive pressure that happens after a cold?

Wawrzyniek, Emma: We think specifically about being in an airplane where you have static change in the umbo location. It's something we've talked about and something we could definitely test, but we haven't gotten to specifically tested that yet.

Nakajima, Heidi: I'd like to say something about that. When you have a cold, you can't hear very well anyway. If you have negative pressure in your middle ear cavity, this produces tension in the eardrum and stiffness in your eardrum, and so your ear is not going to transmit sound as well. The same thing with our device in a sick person. It may be a little bit less because our sensor impedance is a little bit higher than the whole ossicular chain with the umbo but I suspect it would be the same thing.

Allen, Jont: To amplify your point, when you're in the airplane, you can clear your middle ear space by opening your eustachian tube and swallowing hard. This is not really a big deal. Normal, everyday people have that problem. . . so what? Teach them how to clear the eardrum. Unless they have a cold and their eustachian tube is blocked.

Cheng, Tao: Right, if you ask a surgeon after the middle ear implant when they can start to fly in the airplane, you're going to get different answers from different otologists, so people have a different view.

Cheng, Tao: A question about the recording of Heidi's voice: was the middle ear cavity closed during the recording?

Nakajima, Heidi: It wasn't completely closed. It would be better if it was.

Kitsopoulos, Panagiota (Penny): In Figure 1, I assume that the Ground Shield is the titanium and Parylene C layers on top of the piezo. As you mention in the Methods section, they help make the device biocompatible and waterproof. Have you noticed any disruptions in the sensitivity of your device because of these additional layers? Do they interfere with the bending or making good contact with the umbo?

Wawrzyniek, Emma: Adding material to our sensor will increase the stiffness. A stiffer sensor will not bend as much, thus reducing our sensitivity. However, we have not found the 15 μm layer of Parylene C to negatively impact the sensitivity. If we continue to add material, we will eventually reach a point where the sensitivity goes down. We can model the sensor analytically or using COMSOL to estimate the maximum encapsulation thickness before we lose sensitivity, but we haven't done so yet. Layers of titanium or gold (or other thin film non-organics) are so relatively thin — nm scale rather than μm scale — that we are not concerned about them impacting sensitivity.

Kitsopoulos, Panagiota (Penny): In the Experimental Setup, you mention that the UmboMic is held in the mastoid cavity (I assume the tip is making contact with the umbo), and it is secured with a clamp. In your experiments, have you developed a technique to determine how much contact with the umbo is enough to get the desired sensor output?

Wawrzyniek, Emma: We have experimentally found that the contact pressure between the sensor and the umbo does not impact the UmboMic's sensitivity as long as there is some degree of contact.

Kitsopoulos, Panagiota (Penny): In Figure 1, it looks like the PVDF film section takes up only a small part of the total device, and the PCB requires the rest. Are there any plans in the future to change the PCB and make it even smaller? I assume this would make attaching to the mastoid cavity easier as space is limited.

Wawrzyniek, Emma: Yes, this is certainly a big goal for the future. To reduce noise coupling over long leads, we plan to have the first stage of our differential charge amplifier close to the sensor itself. We want to integrate it directly into the fixation hardware holding the sensor in the middle ear. If the first stage of the amplifier is on the fixation hardware, the amplifier components can be hermetically sealed. The rest of the amplifier could be located with the

sound processor and battery. These components would likely be implanted somewhere under the skin of the skull.

Hajicek, Joshua: I appreciate the arguments used to justify the need for a totally implantable umbo sensor. For biocompatibility, titanium was used for the conductive material, which is not as conductive as the material used in a previously reported prototype, aluminum. The increased resistance of titanium will increase thermal noise. On the bench, do you know how much the equivalent input noise (EIN) changed relative to the use of aluminum? For example, does thermal noise increase by a factor of 15 or some other value at body temperature when using titanium instead of aluminum?

Wawrzynek, Emma: The noise floor of the UmboMic is dominated by the thermal noise of the amplifier's first stage feedback resistors. These resistors have a magnitude of $1\text{ G}\Omega$, and thus are orders of magnitude larger than the resistance of the sensor's electrodes. Thus, going from aluminum to titanium conductors will not impact the system's noise floor or EIN. We found this to be true experimentally.

Hajicek, Joshua: Regarding Figure 4, can you elaborate on how anatomical differences contribute to the variability?

Wawrzynek, Emma: By "anatomical differences", we are referring to the mechanical variations between people's ossicular chains. A tighter or looser ossicular chain will result in different movement. Although all ossicles move uniquely across people, there are common trends shared by all. Because the frequency response of our sensor mirrors the umbo's motion, differences in umbo motion will lead to differences in the frequency response.

Hajicek, Joshua: It may be an overclaim that the results presented here "prove" the use of titanium does not increase the noise floor of the device. For instance, at 8 kHz, there is roughly a $<15\text{ dB}$ difference in EINs. It's also unclear how much of this is due to aluminum versus titanium. If the thermal noise of titanium is significantly higher, this should increase the EIN of your device significantly. A suggestion is to revise this statement in terms of the typical noise of a quiet room. Given hearing loss, the increase in EIN by adopting titanium is unlikely to affect the perceptual/effective performance of the device.

Wawrzynek, Emma: As stated before, use of titanium does not impact the noise floor of the system. The plot of EIN is not showing results from an aluminum sensor, as the EIN values were identical. The EIN plot is comparing EIN of an UmboMic with and without the outer ear. The black line plots the EIN of a commercially available hearing aid microphone.